

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MODERN CONCEPTS OF BIBLIOGRAPHY AND BIBLIOGRAPHIC ACTIVITY

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Abstract

The informatization of society imposes important tasks on bibliographic activity. In connection with independence, bibliographic studies and bibliographic activity are experiencing a period of development, dealing with such a global problem as raising the country's information resources to the world level and providing information to society as a whole. The insufficient study of the theory of bibliographic studies and bibliographic activity and the formation of the resource base, the lack of a sufficient theoretical base in the field, the need to create new ideas and concepts make it urgent to conduct research in this area. In this regard, the systematic study of bibliographic studies and bibliographic activity in our republic and abroad, the analysis of their component composition, and the development of theoretical foundations for their optimal development are important problems ahead. In this regard, the main task of the article on the topic "Comparative analysis of modern concepts of bibliography and bibliographic activity" is to investigate the theoretical basis in the field and bring it into scientific circulation. In this aspect, a comprehensive study was conducted in the article, which was used in the works of local and foreign authors.

Keywords: Bibliography, bibliographic activity, document flow, theory, concept.

Research methods of the article. Complex methods were used in the preparation of the article. Documents on the field were analyzed, while the systematic approach method was taken as a basis, the works of scientists related to the field in foreign countries and our republic were studied, historical-sociological, statistical, bibliographic, comparative analysis and systematic approach methods were used.

Source study basis of the article. We would like to inform you that fundamental scientific research works have been published in foreign indexed journals related to the general theory and methodology of bibliographic studies and bibliographic activity, as well as the flow of documents in this field, as examples of which we can mention the following. (İsmayilov;Khalafova, 2022A); (İsmayilov;Khalafova, 2022b); (İsmayilov, 2022); ((İsmayilov;Khalafova, 2022); (İsmayilov;Bayramova, 2022); (İsmayilov;Mahammadli;Khudiyeva, 2022); (İsmayilov; Khudiyeva, 2022); (İsmayilov;Ganbarova, 2022); (İsmayilov;Gasimli, 2022); (Gasimli, 2022); (İsmayilov; Guliyev 2022); (İsmayilov; Sadigova, 2022); (İsmayilov; Gasimli, 2023); (İsmayilov;Mammadov, 2023); (İsmayilov; Əfəndiyev, 2023); İsmayilov;Khalafova, 2023a); (İsmayilov;Khalafova, 2023b); (İsmayilov;İslamov;Yusifova,2024); (İsmayilov;Khalafova, 2024a); (İsmayilov;Khalafova, 2024b); (Khalafova, İsmayilov; 2024).

Introduction.

The term bibliography originated in Ancient Greece and previously meant "book writing". The work of the Greek scientist and poet Kollimakhi (310–240 BC) "Tables of all those who distinguished themselves

in various sciences and everything they wrote" is considered the first bibliographic example. After the printing of books, bibliography began to take shape as a field of science and practical activity that records and records printed works, systematizes them, describes, recommends and promotes them. The first bibliographic collections in Azerbaijan were called "Kitabiyat". A number of exegesis, name dictionaries also carry a bibliographic function. Starting from the 10s of the 20th century, bibliography in Azerbaijan has been developing on scientific grounds. It should be noted that the main essence of the article is the emergence and development of theoretical bases and concepts existing in Azerbaijan and foreign countries in the field of bibliographic studies and bibliographic activity, its importance in bibliographic activity, and the trends in the creation of new theories and concepts related to the period and time.

Foreign experience. The conceptual ideas of V.S. Zubov are used in the formation of the theoretical basis of bibliography and its relatively correct designation in the use of bibliographic information. Today, the availability of computer technology lays the foundation for a new trend in the field of bibliographic activity. Bibliographic information is rapidly created and promptly transmitted in accordance with the requirements of the era and time (14).

It is necessary to agree with the opinion of the well-known Russian scientist Y.A. Shreider that "The term bibliography does not need any other term, but it is important to understand the change in the course of the research subject itself" (12).

Modern theorists view bibliography as a scientific phenomenon, confirming the theoretical idea that culture, together with social parameters, is a field of human activity. Currently, the science of bibliography is divided into three stages (13):

1. Classical bibliography and ontology as a form of self-awareness (XVII-XIX centuries)
2. Non-classical bibliography (early XX century-present period) and epistemology as a form of self-awareness (mid-XIX century-present period)
3. Neo-classical bibliography and methodology as a form of self-awareness (present period)

If we involve the development of bibliography and bibliographic activity in the study with certain historical stages, it can be said that in Europe at the end of the XVI century, at the beginning of the XVII century, as a result of experimental bibliographic activity in Italy, a bibliographic resource was created in the form of a bibliographic dictionary of the country's writers. For example, works such as M. Rossianti and L. Ferini's "Catalogue of Florentine Writers" (1589), and I. Alberici's "Abridged Catalogue of the Famous Writers of Venice" (1665) are the products of experimental bibliographic activity. In the 18th century, such dictionaries were published in countries such as France, Germany, Great Britain, and Austria (19).

In Russia, experimental bibliographic activity began to emerge at the beginning of the 19th century. 26 indexes and lists of local history published until 1861 are known to science. Among these indexes, there are quite rich indexes, such as P.V. Khavinova's "Index of historical sources and geography of Moscow" (1839). Retrospective local history indexes began to be compiled in the 80s-90s of the 19th century. For example, bibliographic indexes such as "Bibliography of Siberia" (1891-1892) and "Bibliography of Asia" (1891-1894) were created (11).

In the second half of the 19th century, there were two trends in the development of bibliographic activity in Russia: on the one hand, the study of historical and archaeological documents, and on the other hand, the complex study of individual regions and the compilation of bibliographic indicators based on this research.

Local experience.

Although bibliographic activity in Azerbaijan has undergone a rich and complex development, theoretical ideas about it began to emerge at the beginning of the 20th century. The Azerbaijan Research and Publication Society, founded in 1923, paid serious attention to bibliographic work from the very first days, and a special bibliographic bureau was organized to deal with this work, and its leadership was entrusted to the prominent literary critic, professor of Azerbaijan State University A.V. Bagri. The Bibliographic Bureau was given a specific task: to compile a bibliography of Azerbaijani studies in a short time. Since no serious work was carried out in the field of preparing a bibliography of existing literature about Azerbaijan, the members of the Bureau faced great difficulties. Therefore, the Bureau first of all set the goal of compiling an "incomplete, albeit alphabetical index of printed materials about Azerbaijan" (11).

In the organization of library and information services to the population in the Republic of Azerbaijan, librarianship and bibliography have historically worked together and complemented each other. In the parallel development of these two sciences, well-known scientists in the field have worked shoulder to shoulder (12).

One of them is Abuzar Khalafov, Honored Scientist of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Academician of the International Academy of Informatization, Presidential Scholar, "Shohrat" Order Holder, President of the Azerbaijan Librarians' Society, Honorary Doctor of Baku State University, Doctor of History, Professor. One of the historical services of Professor Abuzar Khalafov, the founder of national library science in Azerbaijan and one of the organizers of higher library education, to our people is connected with the establishment of the Faculty of Library Science at Baku State University. The great services of the famous writer Suleyman Rahimov, academicians Abdulla Garayev, Shafaat Mehdiyev and others were instrumental in the establishment and development of today's Faculty of Library Science and Information. Well-known intellectuals highly value book culture and library and bibliographic work, and have shown great concern for the training of librarians and bibliographers, the development of the field, and the training of scholars in this field.

Professor A. Khalafov, who has been the Dean of the Faculty of Library Science and Head of the Department of "Library Studies and Bibliography" since 1963, has made serious efforts to develop both the faculty and the department on modern scientific foundations. Since that time, the employees of the department have mainly worked on the history of library work, the theory, organization and methodological issues of library science, important problems of library and bibliographic service to students, as well as important directions of bibliographic activity until the establishment of the Department of Bibliography, and the creation of a theoretical basis for library and bibliographic science. The study of the history of the development of bibliographic science in Azerbaijan shows that the center of scientific thought in this field was the Department of Bibliography (until 1968, the Department of Library and Bibliography) of Baku State University. Aliheydar Gahramanov, the founder of bibliographic ideas in Azerbaijan, worked in this department and created the first textbooks on bibliography (18).

Since 1947, the first head of the Department of Library Science and Bibliography was Aliheydar Gahramanov, a well-known Azerbaijani intellectual. He headed the Department of Library Science and Bibliography until 1959, gave lectures on various fields of library science and bibliography, played an important role in the formation of the theoretical basis in the field, and was closely involved in the organization of the educational process in the Department of Library Science, the development of curricula, and programs. Aliheydar Gahramanov, a well-known scientist, professional bibliographer, one of the founders of bibliography in Azerbaijan, who worked as the head of the Republican State Book Chamber and headed the Department of Library Science and Bibliography until 1959, is the author of

the first textbooks on bibliography. A. Gahramanov, who worked on the topic of "Russian-Azerbaijani Literary Relations" for many years, completed this topic in 1955, defended it at the Scientific Council of Azerbaijan State University, and received the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. This dissertation was written in two parts. In the first part, Russian-Azerbaijani literary relations were theoretically studied on the basis of specific materials, the mutual influence of literatures was studied, and serious scientific results were drawn. The second part of the dissertation was bibliography. A. Gahramanov, who was engaged in bibliographic activity for a long time, created a valuable bibliography covering very rich materials on Russian-Azerbaijani literary relations. This bibliography, called the second part of the dissertation work, was itself a serious scientific research work, completed as a result of great effort (19)

The scientific research works he wrote and completed based on the republic's archival documents and statistical materials, reports of large libraries are still of great importance for the students and teachers of the faculty today. As a result of his research, Zohrab Aliyev published textbooks on the history of Azerbaijani bibliography and the theory of bibliography in the 70s of the 20th century. Professor Z.H. Aliyev has systematically studied the history of Azerbaijani bibliography over the past hundred years. In his published works on this problem, the evolutionary process taking place in bibliographic activity as an important component of cultural construction in our republic was analyzed from a theoretical and methodological point of view, and a new concept was created based on the generalization of trends, traditions and features arising in this field in connection with specific historical conditions. As a result of these studies, "History of Azerbaijani bibliography" is currently taught at the level of a specialized course at the Faculty of Library Science. The textbook "General Bibliography" written by Professor Z. Aliyev in 2001 was an important theoretical basis for the formation of bibliography as a science (20).

In modern times, Associate Professor Nadir Ismayilov is conducting very interesting research in the field of the development of library and bibliographic resources of Azerbaijan, its prospects, placement and efficiency of their use, and in the direction of solving the problem of expanding the scale of bibliographic influence and comprehensiveness of bibliographic provision for information consumers in Azerbaijan in many respects (21).

In short, we have examined the path of development of bibliographic activity and bibliographic science in Azerbaijan, its achievements. It is known that the potential of any science is ultimately assessed in terms of the following important criteria:

- Methodological innovation, mastery of modern scientific search methods;
- Organization of scientific research works, level of theoretical and experimental base;
- Provision of the field with highly qualified research personnel;
- Level of information provision of scientific research.

When approaching the problem in this way, it becomes clear that the theoretical basis of bibliography in our republic has a correct methodological basis and research arsenal as an integral part of the science of bibliography in the past, a certain level of development has been achieved in the field of organization of research work, training of qualified research personnel and their information provision (22).

Conclusion. Summing up the article on the comparative analysis of modern concepts of bibliography and bibliographic activity, it can be concluded that it is impossible to create a quality product in the field without developing bibliography and bibliographic activity in the Republic of Azerbaijan in accordance with the requirements of an information society, without creating coordination with related fields of knowledge and activity, and without studying the country on scientific grounds. In order to intensively develop bibliography and bibliographic activity in accordance with the requirements of an information society in the modern era, it is important to know its theoretical, methodological and organizational problems, to study the concepts and theoretical basis put forward by well-known scientists in the field both in our republic and in foreign countries, and to determine the future constructive development direction of the field.

References

1. Ismayilov, N. I., Khalafova, S. A. (2023 a). On the typology of document-information resources in the field of economy. *Universidad Y Sociedad*, 15(6), 224-232.
2. Ismayilov, N., Khalafova, S. (2023b). The Modern Situation of Using Bibliometric Methods in Library-Information Activity in the Republic of Azerbaijan. *Scientific and Theoretica Almanac Grani*, 26(2), 106-110. <https://doi.org/10.15421/172333>
3. Ismayilov, N.I. (2022) Library Resources: Allocation and Usage Problems (Comparative Analysis of the World and Regional Practice) // – Ukraine, Dnipropetrovsk: Scientific and Theoretical Almanac "Grani". №1 (26), – p.38-43.
4. Ismayilov, N.I. Bayramova, İ. (2022) Methodology of Research and Study of Document Flow in the Field of Tourism (Based on Experience from Local Libraries).- *GRANI Journal*, vol. 25, issue 3, pp. 70-76.
5. Ismayilov, N.I. Khalafova, S.A. (2022a) General Characteristics of Local Lore Documental Network Resources of the Libraries of Azerbaijan (Based on library collection).- *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 2022, vol. 33, issue 1, pp. 628-637.
6. Ismayilov, N.I. Khalafova, S.A. (2022b) Library Sites that Provide Information to Users (Based on Domestic and Foreign Library Experience).- *GRANI Journal*, vol. 25, issue 2, pp. 22-28.
7. Ismayilov, N.I. Mahammadli, D., Khudiyeva, V. (2022) Methods and Means of Information Search in the Digital Environment.- *GRANI Journal*, vol. 25, issue 5, pp. 31-34.
8. Ismayilov, N.I., Ganbarova, Sh. (2022) Organization and development of document flow on children's literature in Azerbaijan (Second half of the

19th century and the beginning of the 20th century) - Technium Social Sciences, vol. 34, pp. 654-660.

9. İsmayilov, N.I., Gasimli, H. (2022) The main activities of the Republic's Tourism Information Centers - GRANI Journal, vol. 25, issue 6, pp. 16-22.

10. Gasimli, H.H. (2022) Researching of the document flow related to tourism in libraries (Based on local and foreign library experience// International Paris Conference on Social Science –VII, – France, Paris: 06-07 iyul, 113-117.

11. Gasimli, H.H. (2023) Development Directions of Library-Information Supply of Tourism at Higher Education Institutions (Based on the Work Experience of Baku State University and Azerbaijan Tourism and Management University) // – Ukraine, Dnipropetrovsk: Scientific and Theoretical Almanac “Grani”, – 2023. №1 (26), 38-43.

12. İsmayilov, N.I., Guliyev, O. (2022) Creation and formation of information resources for children - Technium Social Sciences, vol. 36, pp. 735-742.

13. İsmayilov, N.I., Khudiyeva, V. (2022) Assessment of digital knowledge and research skills and overview of on going work at the national level, forecasting. Concepts of digitization - Technium Social Sciences, vol. 35, pp. 593-600.

14. İsmayilov, N.I., Mammadov A. (2023) National Libraries: Typology, Main Functions and Modern Directions of Development - GRANI Journal, vol. 26, issue 1, pp. 15-20.

15. İsmayilov, N.I., Sadigova, S. (2022) Synergetic foundations of the methodology of modern bibliography - GRANI Journal, vol. 26, issue 5, pp. 45-51.

16. İsmayilov, X.İ., Gasimli, H.H. (2023) Study of the document flow on the field of tourism in the national library of Azerbaijan named after M. F. Akhundov (Based on the analysis of “Annual Azerbaijan Bibliography” and “New books: an annotated bibliographic index”) // – Turkey, Akademik Tarih ve dusunce dergisi, – . №6 (10), 2467-2474.

17. İsmayilov, N., Əfəndiyeva, F. (2023) The Role of Mathematical Methods in the Formation of Scientific Concepts (Elementary and Mathematics).- Akademik Tarih ve düşünce dergisi.-Cilt: 11 Sayı: 4, 2239 – 2247. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/atdd/issue/86362/1538789>

18. İsmayilov, N., Islamov, I., Yusifova, G. (2024) Information resources from philosophy in Azerbaijan. Scientific and theoretical almanac Grani, 27(1), 86-90. <https://doi.org/10.15421/172411>

19. İsmayilov, N., Khalafova, S. (2024a) Stages of development of documentary resources from language studies in Azerbaijan. Scientific and theoretical almanac Grani, 27(2), 70-75. <https://doi.org/10.15421/172433>

20. İsmayilov, N., Khalafova, S. (2024b) Traditional and electronic information resources of the National Archives Administration of the Azerbaijan Republic. Scientific and theoretical almanac Grani, 27(3), 44-48. <https://doi.org/10.15421/172448>

21. İsmayilov, N.İ., Mahammadli, D., Gasimli, H.H. (2023) Organization, development and current situation of the document flow on tourism in the regions (based on the example of the Shaki-Zagatala economic region) // – Ukraine, Dnipropetrovsk: Scientific and Theoretical Almanac “Grani”.- №2 (26), 122-127.

22. Khalafova, S., İsmayilov, N. (2024) Information provision of tourism and economy in Azerbaijan and its bibliometric analysis.-Geojournal of Tourism and Geosites.Indexing in Scopus.Cite Score 3.9.-Issue 4.-31 December- <https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21100286463>

23. İsmayilov N.I, Khalafova S.A. (2022) The role of digital marketing in the management of library information resources // ISSN 2074-5354 (print), ISSN 2522-9745 (online). АКАДЕМІЧНИЙ ОГЛЯД. № 2 (57).pp.194-202.